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An Appraisal of the Information Required for the Production of Standardized Bill of Quantities

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ABSTRACT

The Bill of Quantities is a document prepared by a Quantity Surveyor to provide costs information and itemize the quantities of materials and labour in a construction project. Researchers have developed a framework to improve the information content for contractor's use; this paper focused on the information contained in the BoQ without considering the information and process involved in the production of the BoQ. The availability of information required for the production of accurate Bill of Quantities was appraised with a view to improving the information content of the Bill of Quantities. The research approach was quantitative and data was collected using questionnaire survey. The findings revealed that, thirty-seven (37) required information sourced from NRM2 and BESMM4 which include documents, drawings, schedules and reports and other information. The respondent for the study is mostly involve in Quantity Surveying consultancy services, about 50% of the respondents are consultants, 38% engage in both contracting and consultancy services while 12% are contractors. The experience of the respondents is distributed across the levels specified in the questionnaire but Quantity Surveyors with 5 years or less experience was having the highest percentage. Additionally, the majority of the respondents have produced over 15 BoQs in the last 5 years, about 72% of the Quantity Surveyors sampled in the study. Moreover, the Quantity surveyors considered all the information as important and required for the production of Bill of Quantities, thirty-one (31) out of the thirty-seven (37) required information have a mean score of four (4) and above while the remaining six (6) information have a mean score above three (3). Finally, the study concludes that; there are 16 information that are considered to be critical to the production of Bill of Quantities.

Keywords: Bill of Quantities, New Rules of Measurement, construction industry

1. INTRODUCTION

Bill of Quantities is a document prepared by a Quantity Surveyor to provide costs information and itemize the quantities of materials and labour in a construction project [1]. In a study conducted by Abdul-Rashid et al, [2] it was found that Bill of Quantities are still viable for use as an important document in a construction contract despite the emergence of new procurement routes in the construction industry. Bill of Quantities are widely used in traditional procurement route due to its ability to allow for competitive tendering. A Quantity Surveyor is engaged by the client to prepare a Bill of Quantities on which interested contractors can bid as form of competitive tendering [3].

Various studies have identified issues in the BoQ with respect to its usability and improvement so as to be useful in the recent construction environment. In the early attempts to improve the BoQ researchers

argued that the major issue of the BoQ is its format; In this regard, Blyth et al., [4] argued that the BoQ benefit as checking and coordinating document has not been fully explored. It was reported that some of the major limitation of the BoQ as tender document include presence of error, incompleteness, cannot be used to control project cost, cannot facilitate the use of probability cost estimating and poorly structured and too bulky [5]. Khairuddin et al. [6] argued that the BoQ fail to adapt change and no longer relevant to represent the approximate parameters of the construction. Other studies state that the rates and quantities of the BoQ are inaccurate and unreliable. Net quantities and inaccurate quantities are major dissatisfaction among contractors in the way quantities are provided in the BoQ [7]. The most recent trend in the efforts to improve the BoQ have been proposing ways to solve the issues of insufficient information content in the BoQ. Studies conducted within this argued that the issues are; inadequate information on time related parameters, inadequate information and form for site management purposes, unclear connection between BoQ and construction processes[7, 8], location of information is not adequate for contractor's utilization [9], the information provided does not fulfil the contractor's need for accurate pricing (Morledge and Kings, 2006), inadequate information on connection cost and time related parameters, inadequate information details for contractor's use (Hamimah, et al., 2011), ShamsulHadi (2015) developed a framework to improve the information content for contractor's use, the study focused on the information contained in the BoQ without considering the information and process involved in the production of the BoQ.

Moreover, according to New Rules of Measurement 2 (NRM2) and Building and Engineering Standard Method of Measurement 4 (BESMM4), the accuracy of the Bill of Quantities (BoQ) is dependent on the quality of information supplied to the Quantity Surveyor by the employer, designers and other team members; the more information provided, the more reliable the outcome will be. Where little or no information is provided, the Quantity Surveyor will need to seek decision from the employer as to how the uncertainty is to be managed and procured. Also, when the information provided in the BoQ is inaccurate and unreliable it will lead to disputes and unnecessary claims which will lead to cost and time overruns and/or project abandonment. Vamsidhar et al [10] stated that price escalation is affecting the construction industry negatively as a result of inadequate pricing of the bill of Quantities; causing many problems and many developers to rethink projects. Price escalation produces delays in construction projects, reduced projects scope or projects being cancelled. ShamsulHadi (2015) [11] reported proposed a framework that will improve the BoQ information for the contractors, however the study did not put into consideration information required by the Quantity Surveyor to produce a better source of information for the contractors. Additionally, the BESMM3 states that the Bill of Quantities shall fully describe and accurately represent the Quantity and Quality of the works to be carried out. Hence, without considering the fact that BoQ is a compilation of varying construction information from client/employer, architects, engineers and other stakeholders the proposed solutions will not equal the improvement required. For this reason, a study that will appraise the critical design information that will affect the accuracy of the BoQ becomes needful and timely. Therefore, this study covers the information that are required for the production of accurate BoQs, information requirement specified in New Rules of Measurement 2 (NRM2) and Building and Engineering Standard Method of Measurement 4 (BESMM4) were employed. The study also covers the nature of the information required in terms of importance, availability and utilization in the production of BoQs. The study concentrated on the perception of Quantity Surveyors on the information required for the production of accurate BoQs. The target respondents were Quantity Surveyors who are responsible for the production of BoQs, the study sampled Quantity Surveyors' perception on the availability, importance and level of utilization of the information stated in the New Rules of Measurement 2 (NRM2) and 7, Building and Engineering Standard Method of Measurement 4 (BESMM4). Data was collected using a questionnaire survey and was analyzed quantitatively to appraise the availability information required for the production of accurate Bill of Quantities with a view to evaluate the extent to which the information required are available during the production of BoQs and improve the information content of the Bill of Quantities.

2. METHODOLOGY

For the purpose of this study, the quantitative approach/method is employed. The research makes use of statistical techniques in identifying the information that are critical and readily available for the production of accurate Bill of Quantities. Although some of the variables are qualitative in nature, they are structured in a quantitative manner to allow for easy analysis of the data. Specifically, the New Rules of Measurement 2 (NRM2) and Building and Engineering Standard Method of Measurement 4 (BESMM4) approaches were employed in specifying the information that are required for the production of accurate BoQs.

Moreover, Simple random sampling will be adopted. Simple random sampling is a sampling that every element in the population has a known and equal chance of being selected as a subject. This is the justification behind adopting the method. The sample of the population was restricted to only registered Quantity Surveyors practicing in Kano and Kaduna and the sample size was deduced using the relation in equation (1) [Ref.].

$$n = \frac{N}{1 + N(e)^2} \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

Where: *n* is the required sample size, *N* is the population size and *e* is the level of precision taken as (0.01).

The data was analyzed using descriptive and inferential approaches. The descriptive tools were used in calculating the mean item scores for the Quantity Surveyors’ responses based on the information requirements stated in the Standard Method of Measurement and New Rules of Measurement. The inferential tools will include tools for comparing mean values of responses of the respondents using parameters such as academic qualifications and years of experience, specialization, etc. Additionally, a total of hundred (100) questionnaires were administered out of which seventy-nine (79) questionnaires were retrieved which make seventy five percent (79%), Five (5) questionnaires were considered invalid and seventy-four (74) questionnaires were analyzed making the percentage to seventy four percent (74%). The data was analyzed using a quantitative research approach while using percentage and mean score as evaluation metrics.

3. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In this section the results are clearly presented in tables (distribution tables) showing the percentages in individual variables and their discussions are presented in the subsequent subsections.

3.1 Respondents background information

Preliminary information regarding qualifications were drawn from respondents to give a bearing on the sought of responses that may be obtained from the survey. The data collected are presented and analyzed in the subsequent subsections.

3.1.1 Qualification

From Table 1 below, it can be seen that 43% (32) of the respondents have acquired BSc qualification, 24% (18) have HND, 20% (15) have MSc and 8 % (7) and 4% (3) have acquired PhD and other qualifications respectively.

Table 1. Qualification of respondents

Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Valid (%)	Cumulative (%)
HND	18	24.3	24.3	24.3
BSc	32	43.2	43.2	67.6
MSc	15	20.3	20.3	87.8
PhD	6	8.1	8.1	95.9
Others	3	4.1	4.1	100
Total	74	100	100	

3.1.2 Experience

This was necessary so as to provide a bearing on the extent of experience that may have been acquired by respondents. The Table 2 below indicates that 30 % of respondents' have less than 5years experience, 24% have 6 – 10 years' experience, 16% has 11 – 15 years' and 21% have 16 – 20 years and 8% have above 20 years of experience.

Table 2. Experience of respondents

Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Valid (%)	Cumulative (%)
0-5 years	22	29.7	29.7	29.7
6-10 years	18	24.3	24.3	54.1
11-15years	12	16.2	16.2	70.3
16-20 years	16	21.6	21.6	91.9
Above 20years	6	8.1	8.1	100
Total	74	100	100	

3.1.3Specialization

From the forms of specialization, it was sought to know the specific form of project delivery and BoQs contact by respondents thus Table 3 shows 50% of the respondents are consultants, 12% are contractors while 38% are engaged in both consultancy and contracting. Hence, it can be deduced that most of the responses obtained came from practitioners with extensive knowledge in both consultancy and contracting.

Table 1. Specialization of respondents

Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Valid (%)	Cumulative (%)
Consultant	37	50.0	50.0	50.0
Contractor	9	12.2	12.2	62.2
Both	28	37.8	37.8	100
Total	74	100	100	

3.1.4 Number of BoQs Produced

From the Table 4 below, it can be seen that the responses were able to capture high number of BoQs produced by professional within the last 5 years as 72% of the responses recorded over 15 BoQs within 5 years. This signifies that the professionals captured have the appropriate knowledge that can make sound judgement as to the information required to produce an accurate BoQ, 12% recorded 6 – 10 BoQs and 8% for below 5 BoQs and between 11 to 15.

Table 4. Number of BoQs Produced by respondents

Description	Frequency	Percentage (%)	Valid (%)	Cumulative (%)
0-5 BoQs	6	8.1	8.1	8.1
6-10 BoQs	9	12.2	12.2	20.3
11-15 BoQs	6	8.1	8.1	28.4
Above 15 BoQs	53	71.6	71.6	100
Total	74	100	100	

3.2 Importance of information required from the BoQ

From the observed results it was shown that the opinion of the Quantity Surveyors on the importance of information required for the preparation and production BoQs, as provided by NRM2 and BESMM4. It revealed the minimum and maximum responses (with a ranking of 1 as minimum i.e. Not important and 5 as maximum i.e. Always important). Also, the table indicates the mean which is a measure of central tendency which indicates the intermediate value that have been appraised toward the importance of the information required for the production of BoQ from the respondents. The mean is further ranked in order of severity from top to bottom. The analysed result also indicates the standard deviation which is a measure of variability that indicates whether the measurements are clustered highly around the mean or spread over the range. Where the standard deviation is small the measurements are highly clustered around the mean, if it is larger, they are scattered. Hence it can be deduced that the average of the response falls within 'Often important', consequently, this signify that the information required for the production of BoQs are often important and compliment the required information stated in the NRM2 and BESMM4. While the Standard Deviation imply the responses are not any far from 'Often important' and 'always important'. It can be seen that most of the information of the BoQ are very crucial according to the respondents, as majority of the above listed information have a mean score of at least 4.00. It can be seen that the five top most important information according to mean rank score are reinforcement schedules; plans, sections and elevations; doors and windows schedules; record drawings. It can also be noted that information such as builders works in connection with M&E, statement of drawing construction sequence, hoarding requirements, remediation plan, details of residue and less importantly details of wildlife, all having lowest mean score below 4.00

3.3 Availability of information required

The observed result for the opinion of the Quantity Surveyors on the availability of information required for the preparation and production BoQs, as provided by NRM2 and BESMM4. It was revealed that the minimum and maximum responses (with a ranking of 1 as minimum i.e. Not available and 5 as maximum i.e. Always available). Also, the result indicates that the mean which is a measure of central tendency which indicates the intermediate value that have been appraised toward the availability of the information required for the production of BoQ from the respondents. The mean is further ranked in order of severity from top to bottom. The observed result also indicates that the standard deviation which is a measure of variability that indicates whether the measurements are clustered highly around the mean or spread over the range. Where the standard deviation is small the measurements are highly clustered around the mean, if it is larger, they are scattered. Hence it can be deduced that the average of the response falls within 'Sometimes', consequently, this signify that not all the information required for the production of BoQs are available. While the Standard Deviation imply the responses are not any far from 'less available' and 'sometimes available'. From result obtained it can also be seen that the information availability is on the average while others are not readily available to the quantity surveyor during the production of the BoQs as indicated by the respondents as majority of the information have a mean score of less than 3.00. This signifies that majority of the information required are less and sometimes available during the production of the BoQs.

3.4 Utilization of information required

The observed results show the opinion of the Quantity Surveyors on the utilization of information required for the preparation and production BoQs, as provided by NRM2 and BESMM4. It revealed the minimum and maximum responses (with a ranking of 1 as minimum i.e. not used and 5 as maximum i.e. always used). Also, the table indicates the mean which is a measure of central tendency which indicates the intermediate value that have been appraised toward the utilization of the information required for the production of BoQ from the respondents. The mean is further ranked in order of severity from top to bottom. The result also indicates the standard deviation which is a measure of variability that indicates whether the measurements are clustered highly around the mean or spread over the range. Where the standard deviation is small the measurements are highly clustered around the mean, if it is larger, they are scattered. Hence it can be deduced that the average of the response falls within 'Sometimes used',

consequently, this signify that not all the information required for the production of BoQs are used at all times. While the Standard Deviation imply the responses are not any far from ‘less used’ and ‘often used’. The utilization of information is the presence of information to be used by the Quantity Surveyor during the production of BoQs, it can be seen that the information usage are on the average by the quantity surveyor during the production of the BoQs as indicated by the respondents as majority of the information have a mean score of less than 3.00. This signifies that majority of the information required are less and sometimes utilized during the production of the BoQs.

4. DISCUSSION

In Summary, the findings revealed that, thirty-seven (37) required information sourced from NRM2 and BESMM4 which include documents, drawings, schedules and reports and other information. The respondents for the study are mostly involve in Quantity Surveying consultancy services, about 50% of the respondents are consultants, 38% engage in both contracting and consultancy services while 12% are contractors. The experience of the respondents is distributed across the levels specified in the questionnaire but Quantity Surveyors with 5 years or less experience was having the highest percentage. Additionally, the majority of the respondents have produced over 15 BoQs in the last 5 years, about 72% of the Quantity Surveyors sampled in the study. Moreover, the Quantity surveyors considered all the information as important and required for the production of Bill of Quantities, thirty-one (31) out of the thirty-seven (37) required information have a mean score of four (4) and above while the remaining six (6) information have a mean score above three (3).

The study further revealed that the information required are not readily available considering the importance the respondents give to the information. A drawing showing general construction location of the principal elements and components (plans, sections and elevations) receive the highest mean score (4), eighteen (18) among the thirty-seven have a mean score of three and above, and the rest below three mean score. It was also observed that the information is utilized but only two (2) have a mean score of above 4; a document that prescribes the materials and workmanship required in as much details as possible (4.26) and doors and window schedules (4.07), twenty-one (21) have a mean score of 3 and above and the rest have a mean score below 3. Similarly, the analysis reveals that fifteen (15) out of the thirty-seven (37) are critical to the production of the BoQ considering the importance, availability and utilizing power the respondents attached to them.

5. CONCLUSION

This study appraised the critical design information required for the production of accurate Bill of Quantities with a view of improving the utility power of the Bill of Quantities and to propose remedies to the effect cause by inaccurate Bill of Quantities in the construction industry. The following conclusion was derived from the study;

There are sixteen 16 information that are considered to be critical to the production of Bill of Quantities within the context of Kano and Kaduna, and without which the Bill of Quantity will vitiate its definition. This information was derived by calculating the cumulative mean score scored by each information and ranked base on its severity and information that were having a mean score of more than 3.50 were considered to be critical. Below is the information according to their ranking;

1. Plans, sections and elevations: drawings that show the position occupied by the various spaces in a building, engineering or industrial facility and the general construction and location of the principal elements and components. The extent of elevations and sections shall be as appropriate to cover all major building, engineering or industrial facility zones.
2. Prescriptive Specification: a document that prescribes the materials and workmanship required for building project in as much details as possible.
3. Doors and windows schedules.
4. Site plan: a drawing that locate the position of the building works in relation to the setting out points, means of access and general layout of the site.

5. Reinforcement and bar bending schedules.
6. Room data sheets including coordinated mechanical and electrical services engineering data sheets.
7. Record drawing: a drawing that depict the actual as-built condition of an existing building or structure, including mechanical and electrical services installed.
8. A report detailing the employer's post completion requirements.
9. A report detailing which condition of contract is to be used for the building project.
10. Luminaries' schedules
11. A report stating the employer's requirement for the contractor to collect and report cost data to support claims for capital allowances, grants, value added tax (VAT) recovery and other incentives.
12. Performance specification: a document that describes the requirements of the end product in terms of performance criteria.
13. A report detailing the employer's requirements in respect of insurances.
14. Drainage schedules.
15. A report detailing any planning conditions or informative that the contractor is required to comply with.
16. A report of the employer's policy documents which the contractor will be required to comply with.

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